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ELEMENTS OF SPORTS GYMNASTICS AS A MEANS OF IMPROVING HEALTH-RELATED AND SKILL-RELATED COMPONENTS OF FITNESS

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Abstract

Creating a model of practical teaching for students is directly related to their physical fitness, which can often be a limiting factor in the successful implementation of lessons. Gymnastics as part of physical education includes a range of movements that can affect the overall characteristics of students. In recent years, various models of recreational teaching have been applied to students in practical lessons. The aim of the study was to determine the effects of a group fitness programme based on elements of gymnastics as a basic movement structure on the level of health-related components and skill-related fitness in order to gain insight into whether this exercise programme can serve as a tool to improve physical fitness and would be used in physical preparation for the implementation of practical lessons. The study was conducted on a sample of 53 male subjects aged 19.55 years (+/- 0.61). The effectiveness of the training programme was determined based on the impact of the programme on the level of various components of physical fitness. The following variables were used to assess the level of health-related components of fitness: Coopers test, supinated pull-ups on a high bar, sit-ups, push-ups and percentage of fat tissue, while the following variables were used to assess the level of skill fitness: Long jump from a standing position, Sargent test, 20-m sprint with start from a standing position, envelope run test, dodge and jump. After analysing the data obtained by statistical methods, it was found that a statistically significant change was observed after the training programme in terms of improvement in all tested components of health-related components of fitness: cardiorespiratory fitness, strength endurance and body composition and all tested components of skill-related components of fitness: explosive strength, speed and agility.

Keywords: *physical preparation, practical teaching, group fitness programs.*

INTRODUCTION

The rapid spread of hypokinesia manifestations among students in recent years has caused concern for many scientists (El-Ashker & AlHariri, 2023). To combat the negative effects of hypokinesia, it is necessary to follow the WHO guidelines for minimal physical activity that can be achieved today in various recreational activities (World Health Organisation,

2010). According to the ACSM guidelines (2018), the definition of physical fitness is: “the ability to perform daily tasks with vigour and alertness and without undue fatigue and to have sufficient energy to enjoy leisure- activities and to cope with unforeseen emergencies”. Physical fitness is made up of various elements that can be categorised into health-related and ability-

related components. The design of practical teaching models for students is directly related to their physical fitness, disregarding the relationship between the magnitude of the external stimulus and the ability of the body systems to withstand it (Mayorga-Vega, Fajkowska, Guijarro-Romero, & Viciano, 2021). Teaching models are developed that differ in structure and content (Choi, Y., & Choi, J., 2022), the selective inclusion of certain methods of energy delivery (Lu, Wiltshire, Baker, Wang, & Ying, 2023), practical teaching models with significantly reduced scope and intensity, and models in which the priority of using physical exercises involving agonists, synergists and stabilisers has changed (Leite, Zovico, Rica, Barros, Machado, Evangelista, Leite, Barauna, Maia, & Bocalini, 2023). A common feature of modern models is a different combination of physical exercises performed with different loads, and in recent years attention has been paid to the inclusion of a wide range of fitness elements (Chernozub, Titova, Dubachinskiy, Bodnar, Abramov, Minenko, & Chaban, 2018; Rosvoglou, Fatouros, Poullos, Tsatalas, Papanikolaou, Karampina, Liakou, Tsimeas, Karanika, Tsoukas, Katrabasas, Chatzinikolaou, Deli, Giakas, Jamurtas, & Draganidis, 2023).

Gymnastics is a form of physical activity that includes educational goals and a type of exercise that requires and improves the participant's strength, balance and flexibility. It can be performed on or with equipment, with athletic and rhythmic gymnastics being the two most common types of gymnastics (Živčić-Marković & Krističević, 2016). Gymnasts perform movement combinations with arms and legs in seven basic steps: Walking, running by swinging the shins, split tuck jump, front grip with low leg, front grip with high leg, forward or sideways jump at 90°, jump into a straddle position, backward or sideways jump (Pintar, Caput-Jogunica & Ćurković, 2006). Gymnastics as part of the physical and health culture programme includes a range of movements that can affect the

general characteristics of students (morphofunctional, dexterous, psychological), since the specificity of physical and health culture is, among other things, the development of students' psychophysical abilities (Višnjić, Jovanović & Miletić, 2004). Many studies have focussed on determining the skills required to successfully perform gymnastic elements (Čuljak, Miletić, Kalinski, Kezić & Zuvela, 2014). Sawczyn (1985) emphasised the importance of physical fitness in gymnastics and showed a systematic increase in the differences between gymnasts and untrained subjects over time in tests of flexibility, speed, strength, agility and endurance, while some studies emphasised the crucial importance of physical fitness for the athletic development of gymnastics (Di Cagno, Baldari, Battaglia, Brasili, Merni, Piazza, Toselli, Ventrella, & Guidetti, 2008; Hutchinson, Tremain, Christiansen, & Beitzel, 1998).

In recent years, various models of recreational instruction have been applied in practical teaching for students diagnosed with hypokinesia (Koh, Asharani, Devi, Roystonn, Wang, Vaingankar, Abdin, Sum, Lee, Müller-Riemenschneider, Chong, & Subramaniam, 2022), taking into account the nature of the organism's adaptation and compensatory response to external stimuli (Wilke, Stricker, & Usedly, 2020; Heidel, Novak, & Dankel, 2022). Group fitness programmes are the most widespread form of recreational sport. As systematically repeated forms of exercise, they have positive effects on changing the functional capabilities of the organism and altering body composition (McCord, Nichols & Patterson, 1989). The health-related components of fitness are multidimensional and include the components of cardiorespiratory endurance, muscular strength, muscular endurance, flexibility and body composition (Britton, Issartel, Fahey, Conyngham, & Belton, 2020), while the skill-related components of fitness include the skills that are important for performance in specific sports that do not directly affect a

person's health status - agility, speed, coordination, balance, strength and reaction time.

The aim of the study was to determine the impact of a group fitness programme based on elements of gymnastics as a fundamental movement structure on physical fitness levels. On this basis, we would gain an insight into whether this exercise programme could be used as a tool in practical lessons to improve physical fitness.

METHODS

The study was conducted on a sample of 53 male respondents aged 20-22 years (19.55 ± 0.61), students of the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport. All subjects were in optimal health, had no musculoskeletal injuries and took part in the training programme voluntarily. During the study, they did not participate in other activities included in the curriculum, nor were they involved in the training process in a sports club, nor did they engage in any sports or leisure activities.

The designed group fitness programme was previously performed on a sample of 42 middle-aged female subjects (37 years \pm 6 months) and it was shown that such a moderate intensity programme for beginners, aimed at improving mobility and strength, resulted in positive changes in all health-related components of physical fitness (Tešanović, Jakovljević, Bošnjak, & Dabović, 2018). The same training programme was used in this study. The exercise programme (Table 1) was developed based on the programme carried out by Krističević et al. (2016) and Trajković et al. It lasted twelve weeks, during which the subjects trained according to the principles of group fitness training (ACSM, 2014). The training programme took place

three times a week for 45 minutes. Elements of sports gymnastics (shoulder stand – candlestick, forward roll, backward roll, forward straddle, backward straddle, forward roll away, backward roll away, balance, small balance, hanging, planks, beam elements) were used for a specific time or number of repetitions depending on the type of exercise. Each exercise session (training) was carried out under the supervision of a artistic gymnastics professor and a fitness professor/expert. The training was conducted according to parts - the first part included a warm-up, the second part included elements of artistic gymnastics, and the third part of the training was aimed at restoring the normal level of emotional, mental and physiological body functions of the subjects and achieving the same state they were in before starting the training (Table 1). The programme was designed in such a way that the load was progressively increased from the first to the last week. From the 1st to the 4th week, the exercises were performed with 3 sets of 10-15 repetitions at medium intensity. From the 5th to the 8th week, 4 sets of 8-12 repetitions were performed at a higher intensity than in the previous period. In the last four weeks it was 5 sets of 3-6 repetitions at high intensity. When it came to endurance exercises, the load increased from the first to the last week - 30 seconds in the first four weeks, 60 seconds in the second four weeks and 90 seconds in the last four weeks. All exercises were explained verbally and demonstrated by a supervisor. The most frequently used methodological form of organisation was working in groups of 3-5 people (depending on the exercise and the apparatus on which the exercise was performed) and frontal work. The subjects were divided into 4-5 groups and changed places according to the number of repetitions or the time allotted for the exercise.

Table 1. Exercise program

Goal: improving health-related and skill-related components of fitness		
PART OF TRAINING	ACTIVITY	EXERCISE
A WARM UP	<i>Slow running and stretching</i>	<u>EVERY TRAINING</u> (five rounds with a 20-second break): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Warm up with slow running and stretching and finish with a polygon with different types of movements performed in the positions of lying on the back, elbow and side flank, knee flank and lying face down on the floor positions..
THE MAJOR TRAINING ACTIVITY	<i>Gymnastics (Acrobatics)</i>	<u>FIRST TRAINING</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Leg front reach, leg abductions (lifting the leg sideways) on the floor on the elbow - 4 to 8 per leg – Leg abductions and leg raises to the side, kneeling in plank and facing the floor - 5 to 10 repetitions <u>SECOND TRAINING</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Front and side split - 5 to 10 repetitions – Roll forwards, roll backwards, roll forwards with legs spread (straddle), roll backwards with legs spread (straddle), roll forwards clear away, roll backwards clear away, candle, handstand - 5-10 repetitions per exercise <u>THIRD TRAINING</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Variations of the swing from the lying position - 5-10 repetitions – Back and abdominal planks - 30 sec to 90 sec – on beam -grand battements, forwards, sideways and backwards, scale, small scale - 5-10 repetitions – different swings on bars, swings on pommel horse - 8 to 10 times for each leg
	<i>Jumps</i>	Straddle and two foot jumps on soft mat with assistance -7 to 10 times
	<i>Mini trampoline</i>	Straddle and two foot jumps - 15-20 jumps
	<i>Parallel bars</i>	Swings - deep, back, front - 3 sets of 5-8 swings
A COOL DOWN	<i>Stretching</i>	5 minutes of stretching for muscle groups that were mainly included in the sessions

The effectiveness of the training programme was determined by the impact of the programme on the level of health-related and ability-related components of fitness, i.e. the level of their components, so the following variables were used to assess the level of health-related components of fitness:

- *aerobic fitness* (functional ability of the cardio-respiratory system) - Cooper test 1.5 miles (2.4 km) (FAETKT) – a simple running test requiring only a stopwatch and a running track. The test subjects run six laps of a 400 metre track. The aim of this test is to complete the 2.4 km course in the shortest possible time. At the start, all participants

line up behind the starting line. On the command "Go", the clock is started and they begin to run at their own pace.

- *Strength endurance*: Supinated pull-ups on the high bar (MRAZGP) - often used as a measure of upper body strength. Participants must grasp an overhead bar and pull the body up so that the chin lifts over the bar, then return to the position with arms fully extended. The pull-ups should be performed in one smooth movement. Jerking movements, swinging the body and kicking or bending the legs are not permitted. As many full pull-ups as possible are performed; Sit-ups (MRCDTŠ) - the athlete sits up and touches the knees with the

elbows, then returns to the floor and performs as many sit-ups as possible in 30 seconds; Push-ups (MRESKL) - starts with hands and toes touching the floor, body and legs forming a straight line, feet slightly apart, arms shoulder-width apart, extended and at right angles to the body. Keeping the back and knees straight, the subject lowers the body to a predetermined point so that it touches the floor or another object, or until a 90-degree angle is created at the elbows, and then returns to the starting position with arms extended. This action is repeated without rest, and the test continues until exhaustion.ž

- *Percentage of adipose tissue (FAT)* – body composition, the value of which was determined using the formula (Fahey Insell & Roth, 2005; Heyward & Wagner, 2004): $\text{Body density} = 1.1043 - (0.001327 \times \text{thigh skinfold}) - (0.00131 \times \text{back skinfold})$; $\text{body fat percentage} = (4.95 \div \text{body density}) - 4.50 = \underline{\hspace{2cm}}\%$ and to assess the level of the ability-related components of fitness.

- *Explosive strength of the lower limbs: Standing long jump (MFESDM)* - Participants stood with their toes behind the take-off line in the starting position. By bending the knees with a single free swing of the arms or with restricted arms, the participants jumped forwards to cover the greatest possible distance. The distance was measured from the take-off line to the rearmost heel (cm) and Sargent test (MFESVM) - measurement of the height a subject can jump. The subject stands at the side of a wall and reaches up with the hand closest to the wall. He then moves away from the wall and jumps as high as possible, using both arms and legs to lift his body upwards. The difference between the height of the standing grip and the jump height is the score. The best of three attempts is recorded.

- *Speed* - 20 metre sprint with standing start (MFE20V) - each subject performed 3 20 metre sprints at maximum effort, with a 3 to 5 minute rest between each trial. The best of three attempts is recorded.

- *Agility* - envelope ('zigzag run') (MKOKOV): Participants stood in front of flag A. On the start signal, each person ran along the lines A-B-E-C-D-E-A and around the flags without touching any. When the participant crossed the finish line after running three lanes, the time was stopped. The result was the total time taken to complete the course three times in succession; Dodge and Jump (MBKPOP) – On the "now" signal, the subject runs to the first frame, jumps over it (or steps over it), runs through the second frame, jumps over the third, runs through the fourth, crosses the turning line completely, turns 180° and jumps over the fourth frame (now the first) on the way back, runs through the third, jumps over the second and runs through the first frame, stands up and runs across the start line. The best of three attempts is scored.

Data analysis

The effectiveness of the training programme was determined by the impact of the programme on the level of health-related and ability-related components of fitness, i.e. the level of their components, so the following variables were used to assess the level of health-related components of fitness:

- *Aerobic fitness* (functional ability of the cardio-respiratory system) - Cooper Test 1.5 miles (2.4 km) (FAETKT) – a simple running test for which you only need a stopwatch and a running track. The test subjects run six laps of a 400 metre track. The aim of this test is to complete the 2.4 km course in the shortest possible time. At the start, all participants line up behind the starting line. On the command "Go", the clock is started and they begin to run at their own pace.

- *Strength endurance*: Supinated pull-ups on the high bar (MRAZGP) - is often used as a measure of upper body strength. Participants must grasp a horizontal bar and pull the body up so that the chin rises above the bar and then return to the position with arms fully extended. The pull-ups should be

performed in one smooth movement. Jerking movements, swinging the body and kicking or bending the legs are not permitted. As many full pull-ups as possible are performed; Sit-ups (MRCDTŠ) - the athlete sits up and touches the knees with the elbows, then returns to the floor and performs as many sit-ups as possible in 30 seconds; Push-ups (MRESKL) - starts with hands and toes touching the floor, body and legs forming a straight line, feet slightly apart, arms shoulder-width apart, extended and at right angles to the body. Keeping the back straight and knees straight, the subject lowers the body to a predetermined point so that it touches the floor or another object, or until a 90-degree angle is created at the elbows, and then returns to the starting position with arms extended. This action is repeated without rest and the test continues until exhaustion.

- *Percentage of adipose tissue (FAT)* – body composition, the value of which was determined using the formula (Fahey Insell & Roth, 2005; Heyward & Wagner, 2004): $\text{Body density} = 1.1043 - (0.001327 \times \text{thigh skinfold}) - (0.00131 \times \text{back skinfold})$; $\text{body fat percentage} = (4.95 \div \text{body density}) - 4.50 = \underline{\hspace{2cm}}\%$ and to assess the level of the ability-related components of fitness:

- *Explosive strength of the lower limbs: Standing long jump (MFESDM)* - Participants stood with their toes behind the take-off line in the starting position. By bending the knees with a single free swing of the arms or with restricted arms, the participants jumped forwards to cover the greatest possible distance. The distance was measured from the jump line to the rearmost heel (cm) and Sargent test (MFESVM) - measurement of the height a subject can jump. The subject stands at the side of a wall and reaches up with the hand closest to the wall. He then moves away from the wall and jumps as high as possible, using both arms and legs to lift his body upwards. The difference between the height of the standing grip and the jump height is the score. The best of three attempts is recorded.

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The statistical procedures used in this study were used to calculate the basic descriptive parameters (number of subjects, arithmetic mean, standard deviation), then the normality of the data distribution was calculated using the KS test (Kolmogorov-Smirnov test) and the repeated measures ANOVA statistical procedure, which was used to analyse the difference between the initial and final measurements of the subjects in all tests used at the difference level (0.05 and 0.01) and the effect of the difference with the partial eta squared (ES) analysis. The aforementioned statistical methods provided relevant results. The following variables were used to assess the level of health-related components of fitness: Cooper test 1.5 miles (2.4 km) (FAETKT), Supinated pull-ups on the high bar (MRAZGP), sit-ups (MRCDTŠ), push-ups (MRESKL), percentage of fat tissue (FAT), the value of which was determined using the formula (Fahey Insell & Roth, 2005; Heyward & Wagner, 2004), and to

assess the level of skill-related components of fitness, the variables were: standing long jump (MFESDM), Sargent test (MFESVM) – 20 m sprint with standing start (MFE20V), envelope running test (MKOKOV), dodge and jump (MBKPOP). The statistical programme SPSS version 20.0 was used for the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of all analyses of the TM and TV variables are shown in Table 1. After the training programme, there was a statistically significant change in the values of the results for the variable body mass (TM). The value of the results for the variable body mass (TM) decreased. The effect size was also analysed using partial eta squared analysis and a value of 0.11 was obtained, which, based on a study (Cohen, 1988), represents a large effect of the difference between the initial and final measurements. From this data it can be concluded that 11% of the difference in the TM variable can be explained by the influence of the training programme carried out. After the training programme, however,

there was no statistically significant change in the values of the results for the variable height (TV).

Figure 1 shows the results of the health-related components of the fitness tests. In all tests, a statistically significant difference was found between the initial and final measurements, i.e. the value of the results of the health-related components of the fitness tests decreased in the tests: Coopertest 1.5 miles (2.4 km) (FAETKT) and fat (FAT), i.e. it increased in the final measurement in the tests: Supinated pull-ups on the high bar (MRAZGP), sit-ups (MRCDTŠ) and Push-ups (MRESKL). The effect size was also calculated using partial Eta-square analysis. On the basis of this analysis, it can be determined that 43 and 26 of the difference between the initial and final measurements for the variables Cooper's test 1.5 miles (2.4 km) (FAETKT) and fat (FAT) can be attributed to the influence of the training programme. For the other variables, supinated pull-ups on the high bar (MRAZGP) 12%, sit-ups (MRCDTŠ) 55% and Push-ups (MRESKL) 38%, the difference can be explained by the influence of the training programme.

Table 1. Differences in body mass and height between the initial and final measurements of all respondents

	measurements	N	M	S.D	KS sig.	Wilks' Lambda	F	sig.	Partial Eta Squared (effect size)
TM	initial	53	77,52	10,99	0,29	0,89	6,56	0,01	0,11
	final	53	76,52	9,93	0,59				
TV	initial	53	181,39	7,06	0,33	0,85	0,28	0,23	0,01
	final	53	181,58	7,08	0,37				

Legend: TM- body mass, TV- body height, N-number of respondents, Measurements-initial and final, M-arithmetic mean, S.D-standard deviation, KS sig.-KS test of normality of distribution, Wilks' Lambda, F-results of F test, Sig.-significance, Partial Eta Squared (effect size) - size of the difference effect

Legend: FAETKT-Cooper test 1.5 miles (2.4 km), MRAZGP-Supinated pull-ups on high bar, MRCDTŠ-sit-ups, MRESKL-push-ups, FAT-percentage of fat tissue, Sig.-significance, Partial Eta Squared (effect size)-size of the difference effect

Figure 1: Health-related components of fitness - difference between initial and final measurement of all respondents.

Legend: MFESDM- standing long jump, MFESVM-Sargent test, MFE20V-20 m sprint with a standing start, MKOKOV-envelope run test, MBKPOP-evading and jump, Sig.-significance, Partial Eta Squared (effect size)-effect size of the difference

Figure 2. Skill-related components of fitness - difference between initial and final measurement for all respondents

After analysing the data obtained by statistical methods, it can be concluded that a statistically significant change was observed after the training programme in terms of improvement in the values of all the health-related components of fitness studied: aerobic endurance, muscular strength and body composition and all the skill-related components of fitness studied: explosive strength, speed and agility. It was expected that this training programme would have a positive effect on body composition, as programmed systemic training affects the change in body composition (Fogelholm, Kukkonen-Harjula, & Oja, 1999), especially the reduction in percentage body fat (Kolnes, Petersen, Lien-Iversen, Højlund & Jensen, 2021), and this was shown in this study when it came to the percentage of adipose tissue.

The most important areas in which any physical activity has an effect on the human body (Velínská, 2004) are Fitness (health and skill-related components of fitness), Compensation (reduction of muscular imbalance and improvement of posture) and Coordination (development of spatio-temporal orientation, joining simple movements into complex units, ability to use one's body to achieve a goal). As shown in this study, the programme impacted on the health and skill-related components of fitness, reducing muscular imbalance and improving coordination, suggesting that appropriate exercises, i.e. gymnastic elements, were chosen. The positive effect of gymnastic exercises on physical health was confirmed by Erlandson, Kontulainen and Baxter-Jones (2011) in terms of increased muscle strength in gymnasts. Selected elements of gymnastics performed (according to the principles of using group fitness programmes) over twelve weeks resulted in a decrease in the percentage of fat tissue and an improvement in the health and skill components of the respondents' fitness, as they aimed to increase muscle work, which leads to a decrease in fat tissue, and as the work does not cause muscle hypertrophy, joint mobility and therefore flexibility improves. And this confirms the opinion that

flexibility, speed, strength, muscular endurance, agility and balance are related to gymnastics (Sleeper, Kenyon, Elliott & Cheng, 2016). A good level of physical fitness is very important for gymnastics in order to structure the technical requirements of the exercises on the different apparatus (Mellos, Dallas, Kirialanis, Fiorilli, & Di Cagno, 2014), which allows teachers to properly manage the teaching process and contribute to a better progression of students' skills. Gymnastics is an excellent tool for teaching basic motor skills and promoting health-related components of fitness in adolescents of all ages (Coelho, 2010; Donham-Foutch, 2007). This was also demonstrated in this study, as the programme based on elements of gymnastics had a positive impact on the health-related components of fitness of the respondents. In today's modern society, gymnastics, especially acrobatics, exists in education, competitive sports, other sports, other areas of sport and physical activity, kinesiotherapy programmes and forms of exercise (Živčić & Krističević, 2008). It is almost impossible to find another sport discipline that involves as much variability in movement and movement in space as gymnastics (Bala, 1993).

All changes in abilities achieved through the application of a gymnastics programme have a great possibility of being implemented in life activities as well as in other sports (Fulurija, Perović, Gojković, Bjelica & Majstorović, 2016), and if gymnastics programmes are designed according to the principles of selection and application of group fitness programmes, they can lead to changes in body composition or improvement of health and ability-related components of fitness. This was also shown in this study, as the selection of a group fitness programme designed by experts and intended for beginners, focusing on comprehensive work and improving strength, led to positive changes in the respondents. It has also been shown that the richness of different positions and movements achieved with gymnastic

elements and the use of existing and newly designed equipment on which all these movements and positions are performed enable the recommendation of appropriate training to improve physical fitness (Madić, 2000; Madić, Popović, & Tumin, 2009), because the use of a programme designed for young people had a positive effect on the body composition and physical fitness of the respondents, who must have an optimal level of physical preparation to successfully perform practical classes.

Despite the positive results, this study has some limitations. The sample size was relatively small and specific to a particular student population, which limits the generalisability of the findings to wider population groups. In addition, the impact of the programme on other important aspects of physical and mental health, such as flexibility, balance or psychological well-being, was not investigated. The lack of a control group also makes it difficult to attribute the observed changes solely to the fitness programme carried out. Finally, the duration of the programme was relatively short, so the long-term effects of this type of training on physical and motor fitness are not known. Future studies should aim to address these limitations in order to further validate the effectiveness of such fitness programmes. In order to create optimal conditions for the implementation of the practical teaching programme, it would be desirable to determine the level of physical fitness of the participants and, based on the fitness level, age, gender and requirements of the practical teaching, select appropriate exercises and create an individually adapted training programme that adequately influences the improvement of health-related and/or skill-related components of fitness.

CONCLUSION

This type of group fitness training programme was developed according to the principles of fitness and is designed for beginners. The goal was to improve health-

related and skill-related components of fitness, resulting in positive changes in the tested components of physical fitness. This suggests that recreational activities that utilise elements of sports gymnastics as fundamental movement structures can be a useful tool to achieve optimal levels of physical fitness in a student population in order to successfully implement practical lessons.

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